

PHILOSOPHICAL TERMS IN TERMINOLOGY

Doctoral student of JSPI named after Abdulla

Qadiri

Hulkar Berdibekova

Abstract. This article talks about views on the object of study of terminology - the term, its definitions, which is one of the important issues of today's linguistics.

Key words: term, terminology, linguistics, special words.

Terminology issues have always been one of the topical issues of linguistics. Because determining the place and function of the terms in the lexical layers of the fields allows to understand the essence of the concept correctly.

The connection of language with society is reflected in its lexicon. The scientific and technical development that takes place in the life of society finds its expression in the lexicon and terminology of the language. Terms are specific words or word combinations that embody scientific and technical process and knowledge of certain fields of science. . No field of science can exist without terms. Naming and description of scientific concepts is of particular importance in various fields of science. Each field of science has its own terminological system and works based on them. Terminology schools operating in world linguistics, in particular, "Vienna School of Terminology" in Austria, "Russian School of Terminology" in Russia, "Prague School of Terminology" in Czechoslovakia, how important the terms are in the life of society, in every field of science [1].

Terminology is created on the basis of the lexicon of a certain language and serves to enrich this language. The lexicon of terms, as an integral part of the national language, develops along with it, goes through all the processes of the development of society and language. The enrichment of terminology is related to the development of society and language, and it mainly occurs due to the creation of

internal words and borrowing words from other languages. Terminology is a special branch of linguistics that studies terms. Over the years, any changes, evolutions, discoveries, developments and news in the field of science are expressed with certain terms, as a result of which the terminological base of the language is enriched and developed. In other words, the entry and stabilization of the phenomena of existence into a special expressive form in the linguistic consciousness causes the emergence of terms in the language[2].

In linguistics, the term is interpreted differently. According to O. Akhmanova, terminology emerges only when a science reaches the highest level of its development, that is, the term is recognized after a specific concept acquires a clear scientific expression. An important means of distinguishing a term from a non-term is that it is impossible to define it on a scientific basis. Therefore, the main factor determining the stability of the terminological system of this or that field is its regulation and regularity.

According to Sh. Kochimov, "a term is a word or a combination used in the process of knowing and mastering some objects that express professional meaning, express and form a professional concept, and the connections between them from the point of view of specific professions"[3] . At this point, it should be noted that the terminological system of the language is characterized by its field specificity. According to T.Q. Valiyev, terms are scientific and technical processes, specialized units reflecting knowledge of various scientific fields [4]. According to S.Usmanov, unambiguous words and phrases that express the precise name of concepts related to science, technology, agriculture and art are called terms [5].

H. Narkhodjayeva pointed out the following characteristics of the term:

"1) a term is a linguistic unit, word or combination belonging to the language of production, science and technology, which is a type of general literary language that performs a special task;

2) a term is a specialized name of a specific thing-subject, material, abstract concepts;

3) a specific definition (definition) is necessary for the term, with the help of which the content of the relevant concept can be more clearly expressed, distinguishing signs that allow to distinguish one concept from another, and at the same time, to place a certain concept in a certain classification series. it can be shown more clearly[6].

The process of globalization, which is rapidly happening all over the world, does not fail to have its effect on the language. This, in turn, manifests itself in the lexicon of that language. The era of globalization creates a need to regulate Uzbek terminology. Philosophical terms have a special place in the world terminological system. In linguistics, the problem of creation, organization, linguistic and lexicographic interpretation of the system of philosophical terms has been in the attention of terminologists. Determining the place of terms in the language lexical system is one of the urgent problems.

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